

Scientific article

First experimental results on lifetime-aware wind farm control

Authors: R. Braunbehrens, A. Anand, F. Campagnolo, C. L. Bottasso

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Abstract: *The study presents the methodology, implementation, and first results of the experimental test of a lifetime-aware wind farm control (WFC) approach. The novel strategy goes beyond the conventional WFC formulations and aims to maximise profit while ensuring fulfilment of a desired lifetime. Damage due to fatigue is formulated using a cost model and is also limited by a lifetime constraint. The control strategy is based on yaw-induced wake steering and utilises a tool chain of power and damage estimators. The experiment was conducted with three model turbines in a boundary layer wind tunnel, which allowed the simulation of a realistic dynamic variation of the wind direction. The novel strategy is compared to conventional greedy operation, as well as to the classical maximum power strategy. The results show that the novel control strategy can improve the economic performance of the farm.*

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